

Jump for Social Justice!

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The *Journal of Underrepresented and Minority Progress (JUMP)*, a scholarly refereed journal, is founded against the backdrop of colossal political upheavals further marginalizing the lives of minorities around the world. United States, on the cusp of being a nation of many minorities is troubled with tensions about whether it respects and welcomes minorities and immigrants at all. The 28th annual world report by the Human Rights Watch (HRW) warned that the surge of authoritarian populists worldwide seems increasingly inevitable, with the United Kingdom preoccupied by Brexit and United States led "by a president who displays a disturbing fondness for rights-trampling strongmen." The report warned against the tendency of demagogues who rose to power by "demonizing unpopular minorities, attacking human rights principles, and fueling distrust of democratic institutions" (HRW, 2018, p. 15). We are truly at a precarious juncture of human civilization because the US and the UK, so far looked upon as the "defenders of human rights" globally have been beleaguered by nationalism. We must keep our hopes that governments' actions will align more and more with various interest groups advancing civil rights and democracy. There is some hope in the policies adopted by Germany, France, and their European Union partners, even though they too have been bedeviled by groups driven by racism and bigotry. Such democracies as Australia, Brazil, Indonesia, Japan, and South Africa exist, but their voice for human rights is not the loudest always (HRW, 2017). There is, thus, an urgent and critical need for a scholarly discourse that identifies and describes the problems, provides a forum for analysis and solutions, and serves as a vehicle for sharing statistics and research nationally and internationally. As Bourdieu (2003, p. 11) reminded, we as social scientists "cannot stand aside, neutral and indifferent, from the struggles in which the future of the world is at stake." We have no option but to jump for the advancement of social justice.

JUMP aims to advance knowledge about the progress of marginalized communities through theoretical and empirically-based research articles, book reviews, narrative essays, and reflective writing about positive changes and challenges, and emerging policies and practices. *JUMP* is an interdisciplinary, peer-reviewed publication dedicated to sharing knowledge about the progress of minority and underrepresented communities in and across different social and national contexts. The Journal is international in scope and includes work by scholars in a wide range of academic fields including education, psychology, religion, sociology, business, social work, anthropology, and philosophy. The Journal's audiences include scholars and researchers of social sciences focusing their work on issues such as ethnicity and race, caste and class, religion and spirituality, gender and sexual orientation, power and privilege, wealth and income, health and wellbeing, beliefs and value systems, and intersections of these issues. Hence, we

view progress in its many dimensions, also defining minority and minoritization as intersections of identities, privileges, and shared causes toward social justice.

We hope that the Journal will become a vehicle for advancing social justice by adding transnational and cross-cultural dimension to the conversation about minority issues in society. The Journal envisions a new view of quality or process, methodology or theory, or the connection between scholarship and practice, in that we do not judge manuscripts solely on the basis of the product we receive. We understand that some works need support and the quality of others needs to be viewed unconventionally. As Apple (2009) argues, “each of us needs to make use of one’s privilege to open the spaces ... for those who are not there, for those who do not now have a voice in that space and in that “professional” sites to which, being in a privileged position, you have access” (p. 11). Given that in our time, this access can be defined in terms of reach, privilege, sharing, and networking or collaboration, we will use platforms of communication and networking/collaboration to promote the scholarship and also to engage the scholars deliberately, to humanize scholarship, to connect scholars across borders, and to create collaborative opportunities.

As a new journal, we would like to invite scholars around the world to contribute, to share, and to be part of the conversation.

REFERENCES

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